

Impact of Rosemary Leaves and Emulsion on Growth and Carcass Characteristics for Broiler Chickens

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Abstract

The study was conducted in the poultry field in Al-Mahawil, using 216 one-day-old Hubbard strain broiler chicks to evaluate the addition of different proportions of rosemary leaves (0.25, 0.50%) (treatments T2 and T3) respectively, compared with a group without rosemary (T1), rosemary emulsion at 0.25% and 0.50% (T4 and T5), and The treatment T6 was a mixture of 0.25% rosemary leaf powder and 0.25% of its emulsion in productive traits and carcass quality traits. Adding rosemary leaves or an infusion led to an increase in live body weight and weight gain of the chickens at marketing age, as well as an improvement in feed conversion efficiency. The T5 recorded the highest live body weight of 2233.3 g at 35 days of age and the highest cumulative weight gain of 2188.1 g, with a significant variance ($P > 0.05$) compared to the other treatments. The treatment T5 recorded the highest rate of carcass weight with a significant difference from the treatment one, and the treatment T4 recorded the highest rates of liver, heart, and gizzard weights of 3.87%, 0.53%, and 3.43%, respectively. Treatments T4 and T5 also recorded the highest ratios of chest cuts, thigh cuts, wing cuts, and back pieces. The highest percentage of femoral ligament resection was recorded in treatment T5, which amounted to 15.08%. From these results, we conclude that rosemary leaves and their infusion represent safe alternatives to growth promoters, improving chicken productivity and the quality of carcass traits.

Keywords: *rosemary, growth traits, Carcass Characteristics, broiler Chicken.*

Suggested citation: Lehmoody, B.A.M. (2026). Impact of Rosemary Leaves and Emulsion on Growth and Carcass Characteristics for Broiler Chickens. *European Journal of Ecology, Biology and Agriculture*, 3(1), 167-176. DOI: 10.59324/ejeba.2026.3(1).17

Introduction

It was expected that with the spread and variety of synthetic chemical drugs, diseases would decline and become more controllable. However, the opposite occurred: modern humans have encountered diseases that were previously unknown, and chronic diseases have emerged and spread (Windisch et al., 2008). This may be attributed to the fact that many synthetic drugs suppress the immune system, in addition to their long-term side effects, which have only recently begun to appear (Greathead, 2003). Meanwhile, many plants exhibit significant therapeutic efficacy because each plant or herb contains various active substances that God Almighty has arranged in proportions that do not cause serious adverse effects on human health (Hashemi and Davoodi, 2011). Therefore, medicinal plants have come to occupy a significant place in global agricultural production due to the natural chemical compounds they contain, which are highly beneficial and important for their biological effects and helpful actions in humans and animals (Wang et al., 2024). Clinical studies have suggested that products derived from these plants may cure several diseases and relieve their signs (Farinacci et al., 2022).

Rosemary is a prominent example of these natural additives, as it contains active compounds such as eucalyptol and camphor that confer multiple medicinal and nutritional properties (Dardouri et al., 2025). It has been used medically to increase bile secretion, support the spleen, relieve nerve pain, and accelerate wound healing (Enami et al., 2025). Its leaves are also used to preserve meat and fish for extended periods because they inhibit bacterial and fungal growth (Elhadi et al., 2025). In poultry nutrition, studies have shown that adding rosemary powder or oil to chicken feed improves production performance and meat and egg quality, and reduces oxidative stress (Tarricone et al., 2024). Essential oils in their free form often degrade quickly and carry strong odors (Brenes and Roura, 2010). To overcome these issues, researchers have developed emulsions that improve stability, increase bioavailability, and mask unpleasant flavors (Movahedi et al., 2024).

Based on this, recent studies aim to assess the impacts of rosemary, whether in its traditional form or as an emulsion, as a natural and safe food additive that can contribute to the development of the poultry industry, improving productivity and product quality while reducing reliance on conventional antibiotics.

Materials and methods

Chicks and Grouping

The current study was conducted over 35 days, from October 20, 2025, to November 24, 2025, in the poultry hall at a farm in Al-Mahawil. A total of 216 Hubbard broiler chicks, one day old, were used in this Experiment. The birds were randomly assigned to six dietary treatments, with each treatment comprising three replicates. Each replicate contained 12 birds, so each cage held 12 chicks. The birds were housed in floor cages of equal size (about 1.5 m² per cage) equipped with uniform feeders and drinkers to ensure consistent rearing conditions across all treatments. The birds were distributed according to a CRD (Completely Randomized Design), with initial weight balances across replicates to reduce variance and improve accuracy.

The Experiment included six dietary treatments for chickens, with the first serving as the control group without supplementation. The second and third treatments involved adding rosemary leaves to the feed at 0.25% and 0.50%, respectively. The fourth and fifth treatments included adding a rosemary leaves emulsion at concentrations of 0.25% and 0.50%. The sixth treatment was a mixture of 0.20% rosemary leaf powder and 0.25% of its emulsion, designed to test the interaction between the two forms.

During the starter phase (from 1-day old to 3 weeks), the chicks were fed a diet containing 22–23% crude protein and approximately 2950–3000 kcal/kg of metabolizable energy to meet their rapid growth requirements. After that, in the grower–finisher phase (from the 4 week until the end of the trial at 35 days of age), a balanced commercial feed containing about 19–20% crude protein and 3050–3150 kcal/kg of metabolizable energy was provided, in accordance with standard recommendations for broiler nutrition (Mohammed et al., 2025).

Method of Preparing the Emulsion

Herbal emulsions were prepared at a concentration of 0.3% from rosemary leaves emulsion. The plant materials were emulsified by maceration in 96% ethanol for eight days, then filtered and evaporated using a rotary evaporator at 50 °C and 100 mbar to obtain a concentrated emulsion. Next, the oil phase was prepared using Virgin Coconut Oil (VCO) with emulsifying agents (Span 80 and Tween 80) at a ratio of 2:1:4, and the blend was mixed with a magnetic stirrer at 500 rpm for 15–30 minutes. The aqueous phase was prepared from a 5% brown sugar solution, which was gradually added to the oil phase until the final volume reached 1000 ml, with continuous magnetic stirring at 500 rpm for 30–60 minutes to obtain a homogeneous, stable oil-in-water (O/W) emulsion. For poultry use, the final emulsion was diluted from 0.3% to 0.03% in drinking water and given to chicks daily.

Efficiency Indicators

The birds' productive performance indicators were monitored weekly throughout the experimental period. The productive performance indicators assessed were: (1) body weight, (2) Weekly weight gain, (3) Weekly feed intake, and (4) Weekly feed conversion ratio (FCR). This data was used to assess growth efficiency and feed utilization across treatments, enabling an accurate comparison of productive performance (Lehmood et al., 2026).

Estimation of Carcass Traits

Carcass traits were assessed at 35 days by calculating dressing and yield percentages. Dressing percentage was determined with and without edible organs (liver, heart, gizzard) as the ratio of carcass weight to live weight $\times 100$. Carcasses were then divided into major parts (breast, thigh, drumstick, back, neck, wings), and the proportion of each part relative to total carcass weight was recorded. (Kaya et al., 2024).

Statistical Analysis

Data analysis was conducted in SPSS (2011) following a (CRD) to estimate the impact of treatments. The significance of differences between means was tested using Duncan's Multiple Range Test (1955) to determine the statistical significance of the treatment differences.

Results and Discussion

It is evident from Table 1 that the use of rosemary leaves or their emulsion did not cause significant differences in body weight at the end of days 1, 7, and 14. At the end of day 21 of the chicks' age, a highly significant superiority was observed in treatments three, four, five, and six in live body weight, with their averages reaching 650, 660, 670, and 650 g, respectively, compared to treatment one, which recorded the lowest average live weight of 566 grams. No significant difference was observed between this treatment and T2 (610 g). The live weight of chickens increased with rosemary emulsion and leaf supplementation, showing clear superiority over the control T1, which had the lowest weights at 28 and 35 days (1200 g and 1828.3 g, respectively). While the birds in the seventh treatment recorded the highest average live weight at 35 days (2233.3 g), the difference was not statistically significant compared with the average live weight of the birds in the other supplement treatments.

Adding rosemary leaves and their emulsion improves the health of chickens, as previous studies have indicated that rosemary reduces disease incidence. Its emulsion also has an inhibitory impact on many pathogenic microorganisms, both bacterial and fungal (Wang et al., 2024). Improving the herd's health condition led to increased feed utilization and, subsequently, improved body weight. Additionally, rosemary leaves contain many fatty compounds and fatty acids important to the body, and their availability can improve growth, health, and physiological condition (Dardouri et al., 2025).

Table 1. Impact of Dietary Rosemary Leaves on the Live Body Weight of Broiler Chickens (g)

Treatments	Age (day)					
	1	7	14	21	28	35
T1	^a 45.16 ± 0.08	^a 114.66 ± 0.33	^a 189.33 ± 2.96	^b 566.67 ± 16.66	^c 1200.00 ± 92.91	^c 1828.30 ± 150.12
T2	^a 45.10 ± 0.05	^a 110.33 ± 2.33	^a 191.00 ± 3.21	^{ab} 610.00 ± 37.85	1210.00 ^{bc} ± 20.81	2016.70 ^a ± 72.14
T3	^a 45.13 ± 0.06	^a 114.00 ± 3.78	^a 198.33 ± 11.02	^a 650.00 ± 28.86	1350.00 ^{ab} ± 76.37	^{ab} 2083.30 ± 101.37

T4	^a 45.73 ± 0.03	^a 111.66 ± 0.66	^a 212.00 ± 10.40	^a 660.00 ± 58.59	1396.60 ^a ± 26.03	2116.30 ^{ab} ± 83.33 ab
T5	^a 45.20 ± 0.05	^a 115.00 ± 1.73	^a 210.00 ± 4.58	^a 670.33 ± 11.83	1383.30 ^a ± 49.10	2233.33 ^a ± 16.66
T6	^a 45.06 ± 0.03	^a 112.66 ± 1.45	^a 209.00 ± 3.60	650.00 ^a ± 57.73	1316.60 ^{ab} ± 16.66	2076.70 ^{ab} ± 50.44
Sig.	N.S.	N.S.	N.S.	*	*	*

Note: *Treatments marked with different letters show significant variation at the 5% level.

It is evident from Table 2 that the differences were not statistically significant in the weight gain rate on the 7th day, as the range was 65.23-69.80 g. This is attributed to the absence of statistically significant differences in the live weight of the chicks at this age. During (7-14) days, the treatments to which Rosemary emulsion was added to their feed, as well as the mixed treatments, showed a significant improvement in the rate of weight gain of the chicks compared to the first treatment. Chicks in the treatment with 0.25% Rosemary emulsion recorded the highest weight gain, reaching 100.33 g, followed by the fifth and sixth treatments, whose chicks recorded weight gains of 95.00 g and 96.33 g, respectively. During the period between 14 and 21 days, a significant superiority was observed for all treatments containing rosemary leaves, their emulsion, or the mixture compared to the control treatment for this trait, while During the interval from 21 to 28 days, the treatments did not show any significant variation, weight gain rates ranged from 600 g to 763.33 g, showing a highly significant superiority of the treatment 0.50% Rosemary emulsion chicks over the treatment one chicks in weight gain rate during the period between 28 and 35 days, with the treatment chicks recording 850.00 g and the treatment one chicks recording 628.33 g, respectively. No statistically significant variances were observed between the chicks of the other treatments and the control treatment, on the one hand, and between the other treatments and the seventh treatment, on the other hand. Weight gain is a more accurate indicator of an increase in mass than of live weight, and it is associated with the health and physiological condition of the organism, especially since rosemary emulsion has a high content of long-chain polyunsaturated fatty acids (Sirovec et al., 2022). The task supports growth and muscle cell formation, thereby increasing growth and promoting weight gain. This was observed in the birds of the fifth treatment, and it seems that adding 0.50% Rosemary emulsion is better than adding 0.25% and better than adding the leaves alone in terms of weight gain in this Experiment (Dhiman and Chopra, 2025). It appears from the results shown in Table (2) that the best cumulative weight gain was for the birds of the fifth treatment (adding 0.50%) of rosemary emulsion, followed by the birds of the third, fourth and sixth treatments and there were no statistically significant differences between them, and the birds of all treatments that were fed rosemary leaves and their emulsion were significantly superior to the birds of the control group with the cumulative weight gain compared to the birds of the control group.

Table 2. Impact of Dietary Rosemary Leaves on the Weight Gain of Broiler Chickens (g)

Treatments	Age (day)					
	1-7	7-14	14-21	21-28	28-35	cumulative
T1	69.50 ^a ± 0.25	^c 74.66 ± 2.72	^b 377.33 ± 13.86	^b 633.33 ± 9.14	^c 628.33 ± 6.85	1783.15 ^c ± 0.43
T2	^a 65.23 ± 2.33	^b 80.66 ± 5.23	^{ab} 419.00 ± 7.24	^b 600.00 ± 4.41	^{ab} 806.67 ± 7.18	1971.56 ^b ± 4.04
T3	^a 68.86 ±	^b 84.33 ±	^a 451.67 ±	^a 700.00 ±	^b 733.33 ±	2038.19 ^b ±

	3.83	10.47	32.73	5.73	3.33	6.64
T4	^a 66.53 ± 0.68	^a 100.33 ± 9.76	^a 448.00 ± 8.98	^a 736.67 ± 7.10	^b 720.00 ± 5.07	2071.53 ^b ± 16.92
T5	^a 69.80 ± 1.76	^a 95.00 ± 3.46	^a 460.33 ± 16.25	^a 723.00 ± 5.65	^a 850.00 ± 18.46	2188.13 ^a ± 9.19
T6	^a 67.60 ± 1.42	^a 96.33 ± 5.04	^a 441.00 ± 6.97	^b 666.67 ± 6.09	^b 760.00 ± 9.32	^b 2031.63 ± 8.44
Sig.	N.S.	*	*	*	*	*

Note: *Treatments marked with different letters show significant variation at the 5% level.

Table 3 shows the impact of rosemary leaves and their Emulsion on feed consumption by the experimental birds; it indicates that there were no significant variances in feed consumption among the sixth treatments at the end of the 1st week. However, birds in the fourth, fifth, and sixth treatments significantly outperformed those in the first treatment group, consuming 147.67, 139.68, and 141.01 g of feed, respectively, surpassing the first treatment group, which consumed 104.69 g at the end of the 2nd week. The same table also shows that there were no significant variances in feed quality between the experimental groups at the end of the 3rd week. A significant decrease in feed intake was recorded for the additive treatments at the end of the 4th and 5th weeks, as well as in the cumulative intake over the experimental period.

Adding rosemary to the feed may improve feed efficiency, allowing birds to meet their nutritional needs with less feed. Rosemary contains phenolic and terpenic compounds that may have physiological impacts that reduce appetite or slow digestion (Wang et al., 2024). The reduced feed intake is attributed to rosemary's essential oils (e.g., camphor and cineole), which impart a distinctive flavor that may reduce palatability in birds, thereby lowering feed consumption (Elnaggar, 2016).

Table 3. Impact of Dietary Rosemary Leaves on the Feed Intake of Broiler Chickens (g)

Treatments	Age (day)					
	7	14	21	28	35	cumulative
T1	^a 83.63 ± 0.07	^c 104.69 ± 9.40	^a 865.68 ± 42.78	^a 1500 ± 48.61	^a 1850 ± 59.57	^a 4404 ± 74.10
T2	^a 78.28 ± 2.80	^b 120.70 ± 7.62	^a 819.02 ± 105.88	^d 1190 ± 50.60	^b 1750 ± 61.74	^c 3958 ± 182.35
T3	^a 82.43 ± 4.79	^b 124.45 ± 14.03	^a 813.12 ± 89.49	^c 1300 ± 23.04	^b 1767 ± 97.90	^c 4087 ± 155.00
T4	^a 80.27 ± 0.60	^a 147.67 ± 13.56	^a 795.06 ± 74.11	^b 1400 ± 26.78	^b 1780 ± 33.84	^b 4203 ± 496.72
T5	^a 83.50 ± 1.10	^a 139.68 ± 5.71	^a 809.82 ± 48.89	^b ^c 1350 ± 25.93	^{ab} 1800 ± 88.95	^b 4183 ± 154.07
T6	^a 81.56 ± 0.86	^a 141.01 ± 8.10	^a 808.43 ± 60.01	^c 1300 ± 21.241	^{ab} 1790 ± 40.70	^b 4121 ± 277.15
Sig.	N.S.	*	N.S.	*	*	*

Note: *Treatments marked with different letters show significant variation at the 5% level.

No statistically significant differences were observed in the weekly feed conversion ratio of broilers for the seven experimental treatments at the end of days 7 and 14 (Table 4). The T1 treatment recorded the highest FCR value (1.503), while the treatments involving rosemary leaves and their emulsion continued to show significant superiority, achieving lower values than the first treatment at days 21, 28, and 35, as well as in the cumulative values.

The feed conversion ratio is an indicator of the efficiency with which feed is utilized and converted into live weight. The results show that adding rosemary leaves (0.2% and 0.4%) or rosemary emulsion (0.25% and 0.50%), or a combination of both, improves the feed conversion ratio. This is because rosemary contains many compounds and nutrients important for body development. Such nutrients include vitamins of different solubility (water and fat), minerals, and fatty acids (Elnaggar, 2016).

Table 4. Impact of Dietary Rosemary Leaves on the FCR of Broiler Chickens

Treatments	Age (day)					
	7	14	21	28	35	cumulative
T1	^a 1.20 ± 0.03	1.40 ^a ± 0.03	^a 2.29 ± 0.03	^a 2.36 ± 0.01	^a 2.94 ± 0.06	^a 2.46 ± 9.0
T2	^a 1.20 ± 0.00	^a 1.49 ± 0.03	^b 1.95 ± 0.05	^b 1.98 ± 0.05	^c 2.16 ± 0.70	^b 2.00 ± 0.10
T3	^a 1.19 ± 1.20	1.48 ^a ± 0.01	^c 1.80 ± 0.05	^{bc} 1.85 ± 0.08	^b 2.40 ± 0.20	^b 2.00 ± 0.30
T4	^a 1.20 ± 0.03	^a 1.47 ± 0.08	^c 1.77 ± 0.03	1.90 ^{bc} ± 0.05	^b 2.47 ± 0.17	^b 2.02 ± 0.30
T5	^a 1.19 ± 0.06	^a 1.47 ± 0.01	^{bc} 1.86 ± 0.08	1.75 ^c ± 0.02	^c 2.11 ± 0.15	^b 1.91 ± 0.26
T6	^a 1.20 ± 0.03	^a 1.46 ± 0.08	^b 1.94 ± 0.03	1.83 ^{bc} ± 0.01	^b 2.35 ± 0.05	^b 2.02 ± 0.03
Sig.	N.S	N.S	*	*	*	*

Note: *Treatments marked with different letters show significant variation at the 5% level.

The results in Table 5 indicate significant differences in dressed carcass weight among the experimental treatments, with the fifth treatment achieving the highest weight at 1528.30 g, compared to the first treatment, which had an average dressed carcass weight of 1234.43 g. Meanwhile, no significant differences were observed among the other treatments. The moral and arithmetic superiority of the experimental coefficients in the weight of the carcass compared to the first treatment is mainly attributed to the high weight of the live broilers, because the weight of the cleaned carcass is highly correlated with the weight of the live bird (Nagre et al., 2024).

As for the Carcass yield with viscera and Carcass yield without viscera percentages, they were not significantly different among meat chicken breeds. The treatment recorded that the addition of 0.25% rosemary emulsion resulted in the highest evisceration yield with internal organs, reaching 76.04%. Likewise, the significant improvement in evisceration yield with edible viscera for the fourth treatment, which used 0.25% rosemary emulsion, is also due to the increase in the proportions of edible viscera, namely the liver, heart, and gizzard, which accounted for 3.80% of liver weight, 0.53% of heart weight,

and 3.43% of gizzard weight (Table 5). Meanwhile, the first treatment recorded the lowest percentages, reaching 2.72% for liver weight, 0.51% for heart weight, and 2.46% for gizzard weight.

It is evident that adding rosemary emulsion at a concentration of 0.25% is likely to increase fat metabolism, thereby enlarging the liver and increasing its weight, as the liver is the main organ responsible for fat metabolism in the body (Abou-Kassem et al., 2021). The reason may be increased fat metabolism caused by the phenolic compounds and antioxidants in rosemary, leading to greater metabolic activity, liver enlargement, and weight gain (Puvača et al., 2022). It may be due to improved blood circulation and increased metabolic activity, as antioxidants in rosemary enhance the heart's efficiency in pumping blood, leading to an increase in its weight and size (Apaydın Yıldırım et al., 2018). Rosemary contains aromatic compounds and essential oils that may increase the firmness of dietary fibers and stimulate mechanical digestion in the gizzard, thereby enhancing muscular activity and increasing its weight through hypertrophy of muscle fibers (Puvača et al., 2022).

Table 5. Impact of Dietary Rosemary Leaves on Carcass Weight, Dressing Percentage, and Edible Offal Percentage of Broiler Chickens

Treatments	Cleaned carcass weight	Carcass yield without viscera	Carcass yield with viscera	Liver %	Heart %	Gizzard %
T1	^c 1234.43 ± 100.30	^a 67.52 ± 0.15	^a 73.22 ± 0.16	^c 2.72 ± 0.030	^b 0.51 ± 0.003	^c 2.46 ± 0.07
T2	^b 1367.45 ± 0.32	^a 67.78 ± 0.32	^a 74.18 ± 0.44	^{bc} 3.07 ± 55.53	^b 0.51 ± 0.003	^{ab} 2.80 ± 0.36
T3	^{ab} 1420.57 ± 68.87	^a 68.19 ± 0.04	^a 75.83 ± 0.29	^a 3.87 ± 0.01	^{ab} 0.52 ± 0.005	^{ab} 3.24 ± 0.31
T4	^{ab} 1445.53 ± 59.31	^a 68.28 ± 0.11	^a 76.04 ± 0.30	^a 3.80 ± 0.005	^a 0.53 ± 0.005	^a 3.43 ± 0.09
T5	^a 1528.30 ± 14.43	^a 68.43 ± 0.25	^a 75.46 ± 0.29	^b 3.31 ± 0.28	^{ab} 0.52 ± 0.005	^{ab} 3.19 ± 0.35
T6	^{ab} 1421.47 ± 40.40	^a 68.43 ± 0.30	^a 75.07 ± 0.81	^b 3.41 ± 0.31	^b 0.51 ± 0.03	^{abc} 2.71 ± 0.31
Sig.	*	N.S.	N.S.	*	*	*

Note: *Treatments marked with different letters show significant variation at the 5% level.

Table 6 shows that the lowest weight percentage for the breast piece was recorded in the first treatment of chicken carcasses (24.87%), and then the percentage of this piece increased in treatments T3, T4, and T5. The percentage of the breast piece increased with the higher addition of rosemary leaves or their emulsion, as was the case with the thigh and thigh joint pieces, where the highest percentage was recorded in the addition treatments, with a significant difference. Meanwhile, the lowest percentage was recorded in the first treatment for the breast piece, indicating the importance of adding rosemary leaves and their emulsion to improve the weight percentages of the main cuts of broiler carcasses, with the percentage increasing with higher additions of rosemary leaves and their emulsion. Similarly, the wing weight percentage, which is considered a secondary cut, increased with the higher addition of rosemary leaves or their emulsion. The fourth treatment (adding 0.25% rosemary emulsion) recorded the highest percentage at 13.39%, followed by the third and fifth treatments, which had wing weight percentages of 13.21% and 13.30%, respectively. As for the proportion of neck weights, which is one of the secondary

cuts after the wings, no significant superiority was recorded among the study treatments. As for the weight of the back piece, it recorded a significant superiority in the fourth and fifth chicken slaughter treatments, registering 13.58% and 13.34% respectively, compared to the first treatment, which recorded 12.34%. There were no significant differences among the remaining treatments.

The high percentage of the main cuts, namely the breast, thigh, and thigh joint, when rosemary leaves or their emulsion are added, is considered a good indicator of the quality of carcasses produced from broiler chickens, as most of the meat is found in the main cuts of the broiler carcass (Wang et al., 2024). The fact that rosemary leaves or their emulsion contain high levels of phospholipids, such as phosphatidylethanolamine, phosphatidylcholine, and others, as well as essential fatty acids, can help in building muscle cells, since phospholipids are part of the structure of muscle cell membranes, and phospholipids are concentrated in chicken meat (Petricevic et al., 2018).

Table 6. Impact of Dietary Rosemary Leaves on the Main and Secondary Cuts of Broiler Chicken Carcass

Treatments	% Chest	%Thigh	Femoral link %	%Wings	%Neck	%Back
T1	^b 24.87 ± 0.30	^b 15.51 ± 0.15	^c 13.69 ± 0.06	^c 12.40 ± 0.05	^a 6.67 ± 0.02	^c 12.34 ± 0.05
T2	^{ab} 25.83 ± 0.29	^a 16.30 ± 0.20	^c 13.78 ± 0.04	^b 12.76 ± 0.07	^a 6.58 ± 0.02	^{bc} 12.77 ± 0.36
T3	^a 26.52 ± 0.20	^a 16.30 ± 0.29	^b 14.40 ± 0.26	^a 13.21 ± 0.16	^a 6.65 ± 0.01	^{bc} 12.79 ± 0.35
T4	^a 26.81 ± 0.07	^a 16.45 ± 0.24	^b 14.62 ± 0.14	^a 13.39 ± 0.10	^a 6.65 ± 0.01	^a 13.58 ± 0.15
T5	^a 26.14 ± 0.14	^a 16.34 ± 0.24	^a 15.08 ± 0.48	^a 13.30 ± 0.33	^a 6.59 ± 0.02	^a 13.34 ± 0.32
T6	^{ab} 25.10 ± 0.05	^a 16.03 ± 0.34	^b 14.37 ± 0.26	^c 12.25 ± 0.23	^a 6.67 ± 0.04	^{ab} 13.03 ± 0.51
Sig.	*	*	*	*	N.S.	*

Note: *Treatments marked with different letters show significant variation at the 5% level.

Conclusion

Adding rosemary leaves or their emulsion to feed improves live body weight, weight gain, and feed conversion efficiency. It also increases the amount of meat produced due to higher carcass weight and the proportions of edible viscera. The improvement in these traits increases with higher levels of rosemary leaves or their emulsion added.

Statement of Innovation

This study examined the use of rosemary leaves or infusion in broiler diets. We observe a significant improvement in growth performance and feed conversion efficiency. The biologically active compounds in the rosemary infusion seem to enhance meat quality. Rosemary infusion has been suggested as a viable alternative to conventional synthetic growth promoters.

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